

Population Dynamics and Pest Infestation of Sesame Varieties at Different Growth Stages of the Plant in Owerri Rainforest Zone

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Abstract: Understanding the interaction between pest population and crop growth is crucial for integrated pest management in sesame cultivation. This study investigates the population dynamics and pest infestation across different sesame varieties and growth stages in owerri rainforest zone of Nigeria. The research was carried out in the Crop Science Teaching Farm, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State. Six improved Sesame varieties (MAJIGIDA, NCRIBEN 01M, NCRIBEN 02M, NCRIBEN 04E, NCRIBEN 05E, NCRIBEN E-8) were evaluated under three growth stages (vegetative stage, flowering stage and capsulation stage) in a 3 x 6 factorial experiment laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design with 3 replications of size 2.4 x 2.4 m². Seeds were sown in an area of land measuring 23.9m x 13.2m (315.48m²). Insects visually seen on plants at vegetative, flowering and capsulation stages were counted and the population dynamics of insect pest of sesame at different stages of the plant growth evaluated. Result shows significant variations in pest population with respect to plant growth stages and varietal susceptibility except Magigida variety which was more efficient with minimal pest damage and should be adopted by researchers, extension agents, Sesame growers aiming for sustainable pest management.

Key words: *Sesame, Population Dynamics, Pest Infestation, Varieties, Growth, Damage*

Introduction

Sesamum indicum L. is a vital and one of the oldest oil seed crops widely cultivated in

tropical and subtropical regions due to its high oil content, drought tolerance and growing economic importance (Seyoum et al.,2022). Due to recent awareness on the

importance of oil seed crops, Sesame has spread beyond the local growing areas in Nigeria. Sesame crop is a very lucrative source of income. Sesame seed is used in baking, candy making and other food industries, till cake used for poultry, goat sheep, fish and cattle feed (Khan et.al., 2009). Despite its adaptability, Sesame yields remain low, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, due to pest infestation at different growth stages (Mekuria et al., 2023).

Understanding the population dynamics is essential for designing effective management strategies (Ntonifer et al., 2021). Different sesame varieties exhibit varied levels of resistance and susceptibility to pest and their interaction depends on the growth stages from vegetative, flowering to capsule development. Several factors affect sesame growth and yield, which among them are: weed species, insect pests, and diseases etc. Pest appearance, population fluctuation, infestation rate and crop yield are very much dependent on planting date (Hossain, 2009).

Yield of sesame is reduced due to damage by insect pest. Not much is known about the potential of mitigating pest damage to Sesame by understanding the stages of growth at which sesame is susceptible to pest damage and use of improved Sesame varieties to improve productivity. Efficient research

strategy is required to reduce the effect of various yield reducing factors in Sesame production in the country. Hence, the need to identify the insect pests associated with the sesame crop to fill its protection research gap in the rainforest zone of Nigeria.

The objectives of the study are to:

- Identify field insect pest infestations of Sesame and categorizing them into their pest status.
- Evaluate the pest population dynamics of key insect pests associated with varieties of Sesame varieties at different growth stages
- Compare pest infestation levels across selected sesame varieties
- Determine the growth stages most vulnerable to pest attack and levels of damage of different varieties of Sesame plant in Owerri Rainforest zone

Materials and Method

Research field

The research was carried out in the Crop Science Teaching Farm, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State.

Sources of plant materials

Improved varieties of Sesame were sourced from National Crop Research Institute (NCRI), Bagdegi, Kogi State of Nigeria.

Plot design

An area of land measuring 23.9 m x 13.2 m (315.48m²) was divided into 6 plots of size 2.4m x 2.4m (m²) containing the 6 treatment varieties with three (3) replications each representing the 3 stages of plant growth (vegetative, flowering and capsulation stages) for insect counting. There were 2.4m pathways between replications and 1.5m between plots. Planting distance was done at 30cm X 60cm at the rate of three (3) seeds per stand, leaving a population of 32 plants per plot and 55,555 plants per ha.

Soil amendment

Poultry droppings (9.5 kg per plot) was incorporated into the soil before planting as soil amendment.

Insect counting

Ten plants selected from the border rows were observed during vegetative, flowering and capsule phases and insect visually seen were counted and collected with sweep nets, preserved with 95% ethyl acetate and later identified using samples from Entomological laboratory.

Experimental design

Design of the experiment is a 3 x 6 factorial laid out in Randomized complete block design (RCBD) with 3 replications. Factor A comprised of the 3 growth stages (vegetative, flowering and capsulation stages)) while factor B comprised of 6 varieties of Sesame namely: (NCRIBEN O1M, NCRIBEN 02M, NCRIBEN 04E, NCRIBEN 05E and NCRIBEN E-8). The six (6) cultivars was allocated at random to each plot and replicated three (3) times giving a total of eighteen (18) treatment combinations.

Data collection

After seeds were sown, plant went through 3 phases of growth –vegetative phase, flowering phase and capsule phase. The following growth parameters were collected and analyzed based on different growth stages

1. Days to Emergence: The number of days it took sown seeds to emerge.
2. Germination percentage (%): The number of plants that emerged in each plot divided by the total number of seeds sown.

$$\frac{\text{Number of emerged plant} \times 100}{\text{Total number of seeds sown}}$$

3. Days to flower bud initiation: The number of days it took the plants from planting to form flower buds were

counted and recorded.

4. Days to flower opening / Anthesis: The number of days it took the plants from planting to flower buds opening were recorded.
5. Days to capsule initiation: The number of days it took the plants from planting for the first capsule to appear were recorded.
6. Days to 50% flower opening: The number of days it took the plants from planting for 50% of the plants to flower were recorded.
7. Days to 50% capsule formation: The number of days it took the plants from planting for 50% of the capsule to appear were counted and recorded.
8. Days to 100% maturity: The number of days it took the plants from planting for 100% of the plants to mature were recorded.
9. Plant height at maturity: Distance from the base of the plant to the point of last leaf at maturity were recorded.

Statistical analysis

Data collected was subjected to analysis of variance using Genstat edition, (2017). Data on insect count and damage was first subjected to square root transformation to

ensure uniformity of data. Significantly different means were separated using Fishers Least Significant Difference at 5 % probability level (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

Result and Discussion

Fig 1 shows the population dynamics of insect pests on growth of sesame at stage. Sesame varieties recorded higher population of Brown Grasshopper (*Cantantops erubescens*) on Majigida. Lowest population of brown grasshopper was recorded with NCRIBEN 05E variety fig 1a. NCRIBEN(04E) had the highest population of bean-fly while lowest significant population of bean fly was shown with Majigida fig 1b. Lower population of Green grasshopper (*krausaria angulifera*) was noticed at NCRIBEN 05E and NCRIBEN 04E fig 1c. Fig 2 shows the population dynamics of insect pests on growth of sesame at flowering stage. Population of Social bee was higher with Majigida compared to other varieties. The lowest significant population of Social bee was found with NCRIBEN 05E Fig.2a. NCRIBEN 01M had higher population of black bug. Lower population was found in NCRIBEN 05E fig.2b. Higher population of blister beetle (*Mylabris spp*) was found in NCRIBEN 02M. Least population was noticed in NCRIBEN 04E and NCRIBEN 05E respectively fig.2c. Fig 3 shows the population dynamics of insect pests on growth of sesame at capsulation stage. Brown bug was highly populated in Majigida compared to other varieties which were extremely low populated fig.3aa. Sesame varieties showed

highest population of Green stink bug (*Nezera viridula*) in NCRIBEN 04E; NCRIBEN 01M and NCRIBEN E-8. Lowest population of green bug was shown in Majigida variety fig 3b. NCRIBEN 04E was highly populated with orange-black bug. Lower population was shown in Majigida fig.3c.

Table 1.0 shows the effect of Sesame varieties on growth of the plant (Table 1a) in Owerri Rainforest Zone. Table 1a shows that there were significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among the Sesame varieties with respect to days to emergence and percentage emergence. Majigida variety emerged earlier with higher percentage while NCRIBEN 05E, emerged lately with a very low percentage. There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) among the varieties in respect to days to flower bud initiation, flower opening, capsule initiation and days to 50% capsule formation. At maturity, there was significant difference among all the varieties ($P < 0.05$).

Majigida variety matured earlier at 108 days after planting compared with other varieties while NCRIBEN 05E matured later in 120 days from planting. Plant height at maturity was significantly different ($p < 0.05$) among varieties. NCRIBEN E-8 had highest plant height while NCRIBEN 02M recorded the least plant height. Table 2.0. shows the pest Status and stages of growth (vegetative, flowering and capsulation stages) of Sesame plant. Higher population of Brown, Green and variegated Grasshoppers recorded shows more susceptibility to high yielding cultivars.

Pest population peaked at the flowering stage to capsule development stages, correlating with increased plant biomass and nectar availability.

Varietal susceptibility- Majigida variety recorded significantly higher pest infestation while NCRIBEN 02M Showed lower infestation indicating relative tolerance

Mean pest population dynamics at Vegetative stage of Sesame

1a mean population of Brown grasshopper

1b mean population of Bean fly

1c mean population of Green Grasshopper

Mean pest population dynamics at flowering stage of Sesame

2a Mean population of social bee

2b Mean population of Black bee

2c Mean population of Blister beetle

Mean pest population dynamics at Capsulation stage of Sesame

3a Mean population of Brown bug

3b Mean population of green-stink bug

3c Mean population of Orange-black

Table 1 Effects of Sesame Varieties on Sesame Growth Stages in Owerri Rainforest Zone

Varieties	Vegetative Stage		Flowering Stage			Capsule Stage		Maturity Stage	
	Days to Emergence	(%) emergence	Days to flower bud initiation	Days to flower opening	Days to 50% flower opening	Days to capsule initiation	Days to 50% capsule initiation	Days to maturity	Plant height at maturity
MAI JIGIDA	5.22	66.30	38.78	46.11	56.00	48.33	60.56	108.00	164.90
NCRIBENO1M	6.00	39.60	41.44	48.89	59.22	52.44	64.56	115.33	157.70
NCRIBENO2M	6.78	28.80	43.67	52.56	61.78	55.11	66.22	111.22	144.10
NCRIBEN O4E	6.33	34.10	40.11	48.00	58.00	50.56	64.22	110.44	173.90
NCRIBEN O5E	7.22	24.00	42.56	50.11	58.33	53.00	65.33	120.00	158.70
NCRIBEN E-8	6.33	33.70	40.22	48.67	56.89	50.44	61.78	110.33	183.60
LSD(0.05)(C)	0.58	14.06	5.07	5.37	4.56	5.55	4.99	6.05	19.32

Table 2. The common Pests of Sesame Varieties Categorized into Pest Status

Order	Family	Scientific Name	Common Name	Stage of Attack	Part Affected	Level of Damage
Orthoptera	Acrididae	<i>Cantantops</i> spp.	Brown grasshopper	Adult/ nymph	Vegetative	Feed on leaflets
Diptera	Agromyzidae	<i>Opiomyia</i> spp.	Bean fly	Adult/ nymph	Vegetativ/ flower	Stunted plants/ wilting
Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Ootheca</i> spp	Foliage beetle	Adult/ nymph	Vegetative	Premature senescence
Coleoptera	Apionidae	<i>Apion benignum</i>	Black ant	Adult/ nymph	Vegs/flower/cap	Ragged effect on leaflet
Orthoptera	Acrididae	<i>Krausaria</i> spp.	Green grasshopper	Adult/ nymph	Vegetative	Feed on leaflets
Diptera	Platystomatida	<i>Rivellia angulate</i>	Fruit/ stem fly	Adult/ nymph	Vegetative	Yellowing/ stunted growth
Orthoptera	Acrididae	<i>Zonocerus</i> spp.	Variegated grass.	Adult/ nymph	Vegetative/ caps	Feed on leaflets
Hemiptera	Menbracidae	<i>Otinotus</i> spp.	Brown bugs	Adult/ nymph	Vegetative/flower	Wilting/ reduced plant vigor
Hymenopter	Megachilidae	<i>Apis dorsata</i>	Social bee	Adult	Flowering	Pollination of flowers
Hymenopter	Megachilidae	<i>Megacille bee</i>	Solitary bee	Adult	Flowering	Pollination of flowers
Hymenopter	Megachilidae	<i>Xycolopa</i> spp	Black bee	Adult	Flowering	Pollination of flowers
Coleoptera	Meloidae	<i>Mylabris</i> spp	Blister beetle	Adult	Flowering	Reduce pod set
Hemiptera	Pentatomidae	<i>Nezara viridula</i>	Green stink bug	Adult	Capsule	Pod rot, shriveled
Hemiptera	Pentatomidae	<i>Creonitiades</i> spp.	Orange bug	Adult	Capsule	Defoliation of pods
Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Ahids cracivora</i>	Lady bird beetle	Adult	Vegetative/caps	Twisted leaves

Pest abundance varied with growth stages, insect pest which attack plant at vegetative stage vary with those at flowering and capsulation stages. There was more insect pest at reproductive stage than vegetative stage, aligning with findings by Gebremedhim *et al.*, (2022), who observed increased pest loads during reproductive phases. Majigida variety with the highest growth and reproductive performance despite its high pest population confirms the report that Plants that grow quickly are better to withstand pest damage. This is also in line with (Selvanarayanan and Baskarann, 1996) findings which stated that resistant varieties suffered lesser insect infestation than susceptible ones and varieties under high insect pressure resulted to reduced yield. This shows that variety has effect on pest population and growth of Sesame. The susceptibility of NCRIBEN 02M may be linked to absence of secondary metabolites deterring insect feeding as reported by Meles *et al.*, 2023.

Growth has significant effect on pest population of Sesame. Majigida having increased vegetative, reproductive and capsule growth despite its higher pest population confirms the report by Mahmound, 2012, which states that the presence of succulent leaves provided food for feeding,

oviposition and multiplication of insect pests; and as well, Pollination improve the germination and seedling vigour which is very important since germination is one of the essential stages because if there is poor stand, no subsequent farmer actions or weather conditions can help produce a high yield. The susceptible of NCRIBEN 04E to attack by capsule pest may be attributed to its low yielding capacity which increased damage by pod sucking bugs. This is in line with findings by Dialoke *et al.*, 2010 which states that Pod sucking bugs has been reported to cause yield losses up to 90% and reduce seed viability up to 85%. Insect pest associated with the capsule phase usually inflict severe economic damage to crop. They cause serious damage by directly sucking sap from plant and indirectly by transmission of Virus and Mycoplasma diseases. (Zerewi *et al.*, 2018).

The list of insect pests associated with sesame which were categorized into pest status as shown in the result was only a limited number of major pest. Some of these pests (Grasshoppers, Beetles, Bugs, Flies, Bees, etc) had caused great loss to Sesame and acted as vectors for transmission of diseases to sesame plant, causing serious damage to plants This confirms the report by Dialoke *et al.* (2010) that the brown spiny bugs are key pests of leguminous crops in Africa causing

significant damage and yield loss of between 44 and 100% in these crops. Most pests at vegetative stage vary with those at flowering and capsule stage while only few were seen throughout the plant growing period. Also, the population dynamics of these pest varied among vegetative, flowering and capsulation stages of sesame.

Sesame varieties had effect on crop emergence indicating that emergence rate and initial establishment affect the growth of Sesame cultivars. Growth performance of Sesame was significantly higher on Majigida variety showing it has high growth capacity. Superiority of Majigida may be due to their genetic constitution and its capacity of withstanding water stress condition than other varieties. variety has been reported as one of the factors which may influence emergence and establishment of Sesame (Khan,*et al.*, 2009). The high emergence rate may be attributed to soil temperature, viability conditions of seeds etc (Saleem, 2012). NCRIBEN 05E, having delayed and poor percentage emergence which eventually delayed maturity and other physiological parameters this shows that one variety may be different from another depending on the growing conditions for that field and the weather of the year (Langham,*et al* 2008. The most efficient, early maturing and best

performed sesame cultivar in Owerri rainforest zone in terms of growth and yield is Majigida because of its high yielding attributes and is therefore recommended for adoption by Sesame growers.

Conclusion

The study revealed dynamic interactions between sesame varieties and insect pest population across plant growth stages. The flowering and capsule development stages are more susceptible to infestation, with notable differences in varietal resistance. breeding programs and extension services should focus on promoting resistant varieties like Majigida varieties (Early maturing with lower pest susceptibility) and developing improved varietal specific control strategies to mitigate pest damage and for optimum productivity. Insect pests have significant influence on the growth and of Sesame. The choice of cultivar has significant influence on the growth and pest infestation of Sesame. This study underlines the need for growth-stage-specific pest control strategies and breeding of pest-tolerant varieties. It provides insight for researchers, extension agents, Sesame growers aiming for sustainable pest management.

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